

**Anomalous Hydrogen Evolution on AZ31, AZ61 and AZ91 Magnesium Alloys in
Unbuffered Sodium Chloride Solution**

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Abstract

The anomalous hydrogen evolution (HE) exhibited by the Mg alloys AZ31, AZ61 and AZ91 was studied in unbuffered 0.1 M NaCl solution using electrochemical testing and gravimetric hydrogen collection. Strong anomalous HE was observed for all three alloys, but the rate decreased with increasing content of Al. The cathodic potentiodynamic response and surface appearance of the different alloys showed that the corrosion products were not responsible for the anomalous HE. Assessment of the charge transfer coefficients for the Mg dissolution and HE reactions supported the previously-proposed kinetic model describing how anomalous HE originates at the actively dissolving Mg regions.

Key Words: Mg alloys; hydrogen evolution; anodic dissolution; corrosion products; negative difference effect (NDE)

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1. Introduction

Magnesium (Mg) is the lightest structural metallic material with a density value of approximately 1.7 g/cm^3 , lower than that of aluminum (2.7 g/cm^3) [1]. However, pure Mg is soft and mechanically weak (i.e. tensile strength of about 20 MPa) [2]. Furthermore, Mg is very reactive in aqueous environments, showing elevated corrosion rates [1]. Therefore, Mg is normally alloyed to improve its physical and chemical properties.

Among the most common Mg alloys, the Al-Zn (AZ) containing series provide increased strength and ductility. Furthermore, the addition of Al below its solubility limit in the Mg matrix enhances the corrosion resistance due to the passivating properties of the alumina (Al_2O_3) film that forms on the metal surface. Nonetheless, the AZ Mg alloys show higher corrosion rates than other structural materials, which have limited their use for wider industrial applications [1].

As in the case of Mg, the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) is the primary cathodic reaction during corrosion of the AZ Mg alloys. This is due to the low open circuit potentials exhibited by these materials, normally between -1.6 and $-1.4 \text{ V}_{\text{SCE}}$ [3], which creates a large overpotential for the HER. Furthermore, the AZ Mg alloys also exhibit the anomalous evolution of H_2 under anodic polarization [4-6]. This phenomenon, commonly referred to as negative difference effect (NDE), contradicts the well-established electrochemical theory (i.e. the Butler-Volmer equation), which predicts that the rate associated with the cathodic reaction will decrease with anodic polarization. In the case of Mg and Mg alloys, the rates associated with the HER increase when the applied potential is increased above its E_{corr} , as first observed by Beetz in the 19th century [7].

Even though a number of theories have been proposed to date to explain the anomalous HE exhibited by Mg and Mg alloys under anodic polarization, there is still no general consensus on the governing mechanism in the corrosion and electrochemistry communities. Some of the different interpretations of this phenomenon include the effect of the corrosion product film, the effect of noble metal impurities (accumulated, embedded in the corrosion film or electrodeposited on the electrode surface) and the effect of the actively dissolving anodic regions. A brief discussion of each theory is provided below.

The corrosion product film that forms on dissolving Mg has been shown to exhibit enhanced catalytic properties towards the HER under cathodic polarization compared to metallic Mg [8]. Williams et al. [9] used the scanning vibrating electrode technique (SVET) to show that the typical dark corrosion product that deposits on the surface of high purity (HP) Mg during anodic polarization exhibits a net cathodic activity. This remarkable finding led to the notion that the corrosion product film that forms on dissolving Mg is responsible for the phenomenon of anomalous HE. Further support to this theory was provided by Curioni [10], who investigated the behavior of pure Mg under open circuit and potentiodynamic polarization using real-time H₂ collection measurements and imaging of the dissolving surface. He reported that the dark regions of corrosion product that propagate on the surface support substantially higher cathodic activity compared to the silvery regions. Cain et al. [11] studied the role of surface films and dissolution products in the anomalous HE phenomenon on HP Mg in different test solutions and showed that surface film stability plays a major role in contributing to the manifestation and extent of the H₂ evolved under anodic polarization. However, it has been reported that the contribution to the anomalous HE of the corrosion product on dissolving Mg is low in comparison with the high rates associated with the evolution of H₂ during anodic polarization [12]. Furthermore, direct evidence has been

provided that the net cathodic activity sensed by the SVET on dissolving ultra-high purity (UHP) Mg cannot account for the anomalous HE [13]. Finally, it has been shown that high rates of HE are exhibited by HP Mg under anodic polarization in acidic buffer solution (pH 3), where no presence of dark corrosion product nor net cathodic activity detected by SVET was observed [14].

The accumulation of noble metal impurities due to preferential dissolution of Mg has also been posited as an explanation for the enhanced rates of HE under anodic polarization. This theory postulates that, as Mg dissolves during anodic polarization, the noble metal impurities present in the metal enrich on the surface, so the concentration of impurities at the surface could become higher than the concentration in the bulk metal. Almost every metal will act as a strong cathode when electrically in contact with Mg. Furthermore, Mg behaves like a non-polarizable electrode as small deviations from its corrosion potential (E_{corr}) in the anodic direction will cause an increase in the dissolution current density of a few orders of magnitude. Under these conditions, the noble impurity metals at the surface will always be below their reversible potential, thus exhibiting cathodic activity even when external anodic polarization is increased. However, Lysne et al. [15] developed a model to estimate the Fe enrichment during anodic polarization of pure Mg and predicted poor enrichment efficiencies that could not account for the large rate of HE reported at anodic potentials. This was further confirmed by trace analysis using Rutherford backscattering spectroscopy (RBS) [16] and particle induced X-ray emission (PIXE) [17]. Furthermore, investigations on anodically polarized UHP Mg showed high rates of anomalous HE even though the nominal concentration of noble impurities was only about 1 ppm. Recently, an alternate impurity-based mechanism in which the anomalous HE on anodically polarized Mg was hypothesized to originate on thin regions of metallic iron formed by Fe electrodeposition [18-20].

Michailidou et al. [21] reported that, even though the electrodeposition mechanism could occur on the cathodic regions on the uncorroded magnesium surface, no evidence of this process was found to exist at the anodic sites. Furthermore, the effect of ferrous ions in solution on the anomalous HE on HP Mg has been recently investigated [22] showing that the anomalous HE current densities measured in acidic solutions containing FeCl₂ were virtually identical to those in the absence of ferrous ion. This behavior is not consistent with the notion that electrodeposition of Fe ions, even if it may occur, is the source for anomalous HE on HP Mg during anodic polarization.

Finally, evidence has been provided that the primary location for the anomalous HE on anodically polarized Mg are the regions dominated by the anodic dissolution reaction [12-14, 23]. In a recent work, Fajardo and Frankel presented a kinetic model to explain the increasing rates associated with HE originating at the dissolving regions of Mg under anodic polarization [24]. In brief, this model assumes activation-controlled kinetics and considers the fractional coverage of actively dissolving Mg sites (θ) to be directly proportional to the Mg dissolution rate, as expressed by the Mg oxidation current density (i_{Mg}):

$$\theta = \frac{i_{\text{Mg}}}{zF\lambda_{\text{Mg}}N_{\text{T}}} \quad (1)$$

where where z (eq mol⁻¹) is the number of electrons involved in the electrode reaction, F (96487 C eq⁻¹) is the Faraday constant, λ_{Mg} (s⁻¹) is a constant associated with the subsequent deactivation of the active Mg sites produced and N_{T} (mol cm⁻²) is the total number of Mg atoms present on the surface. By introducing θ in the cathodic Tafel equation for the HER, the anomalous HE originating at the anodic regions is predicted. Note that all current interpretations of the anomalous HE on dissolving Mg consider this phenomenon to be a purely cathodic process occurring on an anodically polarized surface. As a consequence,

greater anodic polarization leads to a higher fraction of active Mg sites available for dissolution and anomalous HE. The following kinetic expression was derived [24]:

$$i_{\text{HER}} = K_{\text{HER}} \exp\left(\frac{zF}{RT} \left((\alpha_{\text{Mg}} - \alpha_{\text{HER}})(E - E_{\text{rev,Mg}}) + \alpha_{\text{HER}}\sigma \right)\right) \quad (2)$$

where $z = 2$ for both anodic and cathodic reactions, α_{Mg} and α_{HER} are the charge transfer coefficients associated with the Mg oxidation and HE reactions, respectively, σ is defined as $\sigma = E_{\text{rev,H}} - E_{\text{rev,Mg}}$, and K_{HER} is a pre-exponential terms that includes the exchange current densities for the Mg oxidation reaction ($i_{0,\text{Mg}}$, A cm⁻²) and the HER on Mg ($i_{0,\text{H,Mg}}$, A cm⁻²). From Equation (2) it is evident that the rate of HE will increase with increasing E if $\alpha_{\text{Mg}} > \alpha_{\text{HER}}$. Experimental validation of this model was provided on HP Mg in 0.1 M NaCl [24]. In a recent paper, Curioni et al. [25] developed a mathematical model to explain the anomalous HE on Mg under anodic polarization. This model showed that anomalous HE is possible if the Tafel slope for the HER on the filmed region is higher than the Tafel slope for the HER on the non-filmed region, which is in line with the kinetic model introduced by Fajardo and Frankel [24].

Even though the phenomenon of anomalous HE has been widely studied on anodically polarized pure Mg, the behavior of Mg alloys has been poorly examined. The aim of the present paper is to investigate the anomalous HE on AZ31, AZ61 and AZ91 Mg alloys subjected to anodic polarization in unbuffered 0.1 M NaCl solution. Validation of the kinetic model proposed by Fajardo and Frankel [24] using these Mg alloys is also considered. For that purpose, HE rates were measured using the gravimetric method for H₂ collection on AZ31, AZ61 and AZ91 Mg alloys during anodic and cathodic galvanodynamic polarization in a NaCl solution.

2. Materials and methods

Commercially available AZ31, AZ61 and AZ91 Mg alloys with a nominal chemical composition listed in Table 1 were used as test specimens. AZ31 and AZ61 Mg alloys were supplied by Magnesium Elektron Ltd., whereas the AZ91 Mg alloy was obtained locally¹. Samples were cold mounted in epoxy resin after a copper wire was attached to the rear part of the metal for the electrical connection. The test specimens were ground to a 1200 grit finish under ethanol prior to testing. The test solution was 0.1 M NaCl (pH~6). All solutions were prepared from laboratory grade reagents and with high purity water of 18.2 M Ω cm (Millipore™ system).

Hydrogen volume collection measurements during galvanodynamic polarization were performed using the gravimetric method. This method, originally proposed by Curioni [10] and further developed by Fajardo and Frankel [26], allows for the real-time HE rates during dynamic polarization to be determined due to its extremely high sensitivity. The gravimetric method is based on the hydrostatic force produced by the volume of electrolyte displaced by the evolved H₂ gas when it is accumulated in a submerged container.

Anodic and cathodic galvanodynamic polarization measurements were performed scanning upwards and downwards from the E_{corr} to +50 and -50 mA cm⁻², respectively, in separate experiments. The scan rate was 0.1 mA cm⁻² s⁻¹.

Cathodic potentiodynamic measurements in 0.1 M NaCl were performed immediately after the anodic galvanodynamic polarization finished with the aim of assessing the catalytic properties towards the HER of the previously corroded surfaces. This protocol, initially proposed by Birbilis et al. [27] and described in detail previously [12-14] allows for the

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assessment of enhancement in the kinetics associated with HE. Cathodic polarization measurements were performed after a steady OCP was achieved by scanning downwards 700 mV from the OCP. The scan rate was 1 mV/s.

All electrochemical measurements used a three-electrode configuration with the Mg alloys acting as the working electrode, a silver/silver chloride (SSC) electrode acting as the reference electrode and a Pt mesh acting as the auxiliary electrode. A Gamry Instruments Interface 1000E potentiostat/galvanostat controlled by the Gamry Framework was used to polarize the specimens.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Anomalous hydrogen evolution during galvanodynamic polarization

Fig. 1 shows the current density associated with HE during anodic and cathodic galvanodynamic polarization for the AZ31 Mg alloy in 0.1 M NaCl solution using the gravimetric method, plotted as a function of the applied anodic current density. Results from triplicate experiments are shown, exhibiting a very good reproducibility. Current density values were calculated from the slope of consecutive individual weight measurements recorded at time intervals of one second. This is the reason for the noise in the curves. The increased rates of HE resulting from increasing the applied current densities (both anodic and cathodic) increased the convection in the electrolyte thus generating noise in the measured weight.

Despite the noisy signal, the anomalous HE on the AZ31 Mg alloys is clearly observed in Fig. 1(a) by the increased HE current density values with increasing applied anodic current density. As previously observed for HP Mg in 0.1 M citric acid buffer (pH 3) solution, a linear relationship was exhibited between HE rate and applied anodic current

density over the whole range of applied current density [14]. Similarly, Fig. 1(b) shows that the current density associated with HE increased linearly with the applied cathodic current density. This is expected because the HER is the primary cathodic reaction occurring on Mg and its alloys when cathodic polarization is applied.

Figs. 2 and 3 show the current density associated with HE during anodic and cathodic galvanodynamic polarization for the AZ61 and AZ91 Mg alloys, respectively, in 0.1 M NaCl solution using the gravimetric method plotted as a function of the applied anodic current density. Results from triplicate experiments are shown. For the AZ61 and AZ91 Mg alloys, the same trend observed for the AZ31 Mg alloy (Fig. 1) was exhibited, with increased HE current density values as the applied anodic and cathodic current densities increased.

To increase the signal-to-noise ratio of the HE current density versus applied current density curves in Figs. 1-3 for further analysis, the data were smoothed by the Savitzky-Golay filtering method [28]. This method, used in a previous study [14], uses a low-degree polynomial to increase the signal-to-noise ratio by fitting successive subsets of adjacent data points by the least squares method. In the present investigation, a second-order polynomial function was used. It is possible that the statistical treatment during the smoothing process results in information on the HE rates being missed. Justification for the use of this procedure is provided below.

The relationship between the HE current density and the applied anodic current in Figs. 1-3 suggests, in all cases, a linear-like behavior for the whole range of current densities applied. This is in agreement with previous observations on HP Mg in 0.1 M NaCl, where the rates associated with HE during galvanodynamic polarization were obtained using the gravimetric method [14, 23, 26]. In these studies, a linear relationship between the HE current density and the applied anodic current density was observed, without any inflection points or

significant features other than a straight line with a positive slope. From the results in Figs. 1-3, the same behavior is expected in the case of the AZ Mg alloys used in this investigation. Therefore, comparison between the slopes of the raw noisy data and the smoothed curves was taken as a suitability indicator of the statistical filtering method.

Fig. 4 shows the typical raw curve of the hydrogen evolution current density for the AZ31 Mg alloy in 0.1 M NaCl solution during anodic galvanodynamic polarization from Fig. 1(a) and its corresponding second-order smoothed curve as a function of the applied current density. Linear regression of both curves resulted in the same relationship between the HE current density rate and the applied anodic current density with identical slope values (i.e. 0.46 ± 0.01 and 0.04649 ± 0.0009 for the raw noisy data and the smoothed curve, respectively). Similarly, Fig. 5 shows the same analysis for the same AZ31 Mg alloy under cathodic polarization. As in the case of anodic galvanodynamic polarization, virtually identical slope values were obtained, which validates the application of the Savitzky-Golay filtering method [28]. Furthermore, it is worth noting that the slopes calculated during cathodic polarization are in agreement with the expected value of 1, confirming the suitability of the gravimetric method for determination of the HE rates during dynamic polarization measurements.

Fig. 6 compares the hydrogen evolution current densities for the AZ31, AZ61 and AZ91 Mg alloys in 0.1 M NaCl solution during anodic galvanodynamic polarization as a function of the applied current density. The HE current densities depicted in Fig. 6 are the mean values at each time point calculated from the second-order smoothed curves in Figs. 1(a), 2(a) and 3(a). The three different Mg alloys showed a linear-like behavior over the whole range of anodic current densities applied. The current densities associated with the anomalous HE decreased as the concentrations of Al increased (i.e. $AZ31 > AZ61 > AZ91$).

The solubility of Al in Mg is limited to approximately 12 wt. %. However, this value depends on temperature and, at room temperature, the real solubility is lower [29]. For additions of Al greater than its solid solubility limit in Mg, second phases will appear. Mg alloys with concentrations of Al higher than 3% (wt.) show the presence of the so-called β -phase ($\text{Mg}_{17}\text{Al}_{12}$). This β -phase is known to be cathodic with respect to Mg, exhibiting enhanced HER kinetics under open circuit conditions. Consequently, a higher proportion of β -phase would result in an increased number of sites more noble than Mg available for HE. According to the theory that attributes the enhanced rates of HE on anodically polarized Mg to the accumulation of noble elements (in this case a second phase more noble than Mg), this situation should result in higher anomalous HE current density values with increasing the concentration of Al in the alloys. However, the results presented here showed the opposite behavior, suggesting that the enrichment of a dissolving Mg surface with noble elements/phases is not responsible for the anomalous HE.

This is better illustrated in Fig. 7, where the charge density associated with HE normalized to the net charge density passed during the galvanodynamic anodic polarization measurements is plotted as a function of the Al concentration in the Mg alloys. The HE charge density values (Q_{HE}) were determined from the integrated signal of the measured HE current density (i_{HE}) vs. polarization time curves for each material. The net charge density passed during the galvanodynamic anodic polarization measurements was 12.5 C/cm^2 in all cases. It is clearly observed that the amount of charge associated with the anomalous HE exhibited an inversely proportional relationship with the amount of Al, decreasing from approximately 43% to 26% for the AZ31 and AZ91 Mg alloys, respectively. A linear-like behavior was suggested with a negative slope of about $-0.023 \pm 0.006 \text{ wt. \%}^{-1}$ ($R^2 = 0.891$). This observation is not consistent with the notion that impurity elements of phases more

noble than Mg are responsible for the anomalous HE on Mg subjected to anodic polarization. In such a case, the HE charge density should be expected to increase with the Al concentration as a consequence of a greater volume fraction of β -phase.

To fully understand the role of the β -phase in the anomalous HE on dissolving Mg more investigation is needed. However, it is proposed here that the results shown in Figs. 6 and 7 can be explained in terms of the amount of surface sites available for Mg anodic dissolution. As previously mentioned, greater concentrations of Al in the alloy lead to a higher fraction of the surface occupied by β -phase. Assuming that the anomalous HE on Mg is associated with the regions dominated by Mg active dissolution, as the concentration of Al increases in the material, the number of sites for dissolution and concomitant anomalous HE during anodic polarization might be reduced. Further support to this hypothesis is provided by the surface appearance of the AZ31, AZ61 and AZ91 Mg alloys after galvanodynamic anodic polarization anodically as shown in Fig. 8. Even though the effect of the corrosion product film is discussed in the next section, it is worth mentioning that lower amounts of corrosion product were observed as the Al content increased in the alloy. This is consistent with the notion that a higher fraction of β -phase (more noble than α -Mg) would result in a lower number of actively dissolving Mg anodes and, in consequence, less corroded surface area.

Furthermore, it is possible that dissolution of the β -phase may occur during galvanodynamic anodic polarization. Fig. 9 shows the potentials measured during the galvanodynamic anodic polarization measurements of the AZ31 and AZ91 Mg alloys (Figs. 1a-3a) plotted as a function of the time of polarization. The dashed line in Fig. 9 represents the E_{corr} for the β -phase in 0.1 M NaCl solution ($-1.311 \text{ V}_{\text{SSC}}$), as reported by Südholz et al. [30]. Even though these measured potentials contain uncompensated ohmic potential drops,

they increased above the E_{corr} for the β -phase from the early stages of polarization (or analogously, from the lowest applied anodic current densities), confirming the possibility of β -phase dissolution. While the extent of this contribution is unknown, it is reasonable that greater amounts of β -phase present in alloys with higher Al content would lead to higher contributions of β -phase dissolution to i_{net} , therefore decreasing the α -Mg dissolution current density. This is better illustrated in the following equation:

$$Q_{\text{Mg}} = Q_{\text{net}} - Q_{\beta\text{-phase}} + Q_{\text{HE}} \quad (3)$$

where Q_{Mg} is the charge associated with α -Mg dissolution, Q_{net} is the net charge passed during galvanodynamic anodic polarization, $Q_{\beta\text{-phase}}$ is the charge associated with the dissolution of β -phase and Q_{HE} is the total charge associated with the anomalous evolution of H_2 . From Eq. (3) it is evident that if Q_{HE} decreases (see Fig. 7) and $Q_{\beta\text{-phase}}$ increases with increasing Al concentration, the charge associated with Mg oxidation will be lower to maintain the charge balance. In simple terms, increased concentrations of Al in the alloy lead to less Mg oxidation. Considering the dissolving regions to be the primary source for anomalous HE, this is consistent with the lower HE current densities measured during anodic polarization.

The fact that, during galvanodynamic anodic polarization, a fraction of the applied charge was associated with HE indicates that some of the electrons generated by Mg dissolution did not flow through the potentiostat to the counter electrode but rather were consumed by the HER on the Mg electrode surface [12]. Although experimental evidence has been provided that the majority of anomalous H_2 originates at anodic regions [12-14,22,23], enrichment of impurities and electrodeposited noble metal ions may contribute to the overall phenomenon. Furthermore, the dark corrosion product formed during Mg

oxidation exhibits enhanced catalytic properties towards the HER compared to the non-corroded metal surface [8-10]. As a result, Q_{HE} is composed of the sum of the charge associated with the anomalous HE at the anodic regions (Q_{Anod}), the cathodic charge associated with the enrichment of noble impurities on the electrode surface (Q_{Imp}), the cathodic charge associated with electrodeposited metal ions ($Q_{Electrodep}$) and the charge associated with the catalytic properties of the corrosion film (Q_{Film}):

$$Q_{HE} = Q_{Anod} + Q_{Film} + Q_{Imp} + Q_{Electrodep} \quad (4)$$

Previous investigations have shown that the contribution of noble impurities enriched on the surface is extremely low [15,16]. Furthermore, even though recent results have indicated that presence of ferrous ion in the electrolyte had no influence in the anomalous HE on anodically polarized HP Mg [22], the occurrence of this mechanism on anodically polarized Mg has not yet been clarified. For these reasons, the contribution of Q_{Imp} and $Q_{Electrodep}$ to Q_{HE} will not be considered in the present analysis. Consequently, the total charge associated with the evolution of anomalous H_2 will essentially be dependent on the HE originating at the anodic regions and the corrosion product film.

It is possible that HE might also be enhanced on dissolving β -phase during anodic polarization. Anomalous HE has also been observed on other metals such as Al [23,31]. Therefore, it is reasonable that the β -phase could exhibit this behavior. Frankel et al. [23] reported increased HE rates on pure Al with increasing applied anodic current, providing clear evidence for anomalous HE. However, the amount of anomalous HE was approximately 20% of the net anodic current applied, which is less than the typical values observed on high purity Mg (normally about 50%). In other words, the phenomenon of anomalous HE occurs on pure Al at lower rates than on Mg. It is possible that anomalous HE occurred at lower

rates on the β -phase than on the α -Mg matrix. Consequently, a higher fraction of the surface occupied by β -phase would result in lower rates of anomalous HE. However, it is not yet clear if HE occurs on the β -phase under anodic polarization. Furthermore, it has been reported that diffusion of atomic hydrogen into the β -phase is promoted during corrosion of AZ91D Mg alloy [32], which would also result in decreased rates of anomalous HE. For these reasons, further research is needed to fully understand the role of the β -phase on the anomalous HE exhibited by AZ Mg alloys, which will be explored in future work.

3.2. Effect of the corrosion product film

With the aim of estimating Q_{Film} for the AZ31, AZ61 and AZ91 Mg alloys, the surface appearance of these materials after galvanodynamic anodic polarization in 0.1 M NaCl solution is shown in Fig. 8. It can be observed that the surface coverage of corrosion products depended on the concentration of Al in the alloy. The amount of corrosion products was the greatest on the AZ31 surface and decreased significantly with increasing Al content. Therefore, from the surface appearance of the anodically treated AZ31, AZ61 and AZ91 Mg alloys, it is reasonable to conclude that Q_{Film} followed the same trend observed in Fig. 7 for Q_{HE} , exhibiting lower amounts of charge associated with anomalous HE on the corrosion product film as the concentration Al in the alloy increased.

To evaluate the effect of the corrosion products film on the anomalous HE of the AZ31, AZ61 and AZ91 Mg alloys during anodic polarization, the catalytic properties towards the HER of the previously corroded surfaces was evaluated. Fig. 10 shows the cathodic potentiodynamic polarization curves of the AZ31, AZ61 and AZ91 Mg alloys after anodic galvanodynamic polarization measurements finished. For comparative purposes, cathodic potentiodynamic polarization curves of freshly polished surfaces with no prior anodic polarization are also presented. Typical data from replicated and reproducible experiments

are shown. It can be observed that the cathodic kinetics were enhanced for the 3 different Mg alloys after anodic polarization. This increase can be attributed to the presence of deposited corrosion products, which were more catalytic towards the HER than the bare metal surface, as previously shown for HP Mg [8-10]. However, differences in the electrochemical behavior of the previously polarized and the non-previously polarized samples were only observed at small amounts of cathodic polarization. At potential values below ~ 250 mV from the E_{corr} (where ohmic potential effects play a role) no significant differences were shown. Interestingly, all alloys exhibited a very similar increase at any given potential. For example, at $-1.7 V_{\text{SSC}}$, the 3 different alloys showed an increase in the cathodic current density of about 3.5X. This is not consistent with the notion that the corrosion products are responsible for the anomalous HE. In such a case, the cathodic current densities measured after anodic polarization should reflect the remarkable differences in the amount of corrosion products shown in Fig. 8.

From Eq. (4) and the results shown in Figs. 7 it is clear that during anodic polarization of the AZ31, AZ61 and AZ91 Mg alloys, the charge associated with the anomalous HE decreased with increasing the concentration of Al (i.e. $AZ31 > AZ61 > AZ91$), causing an equivalent decrease in the Mg oxidation reaction (Eq. (3)). Note that in the present analysis Q_{Film} could only be estimated by visual inspection of the surface appearance of the previously corroded surfaces, thus its numerical contribution was not considered. However, it is likely that the significant differences in the amount of corrosion products observed in Fig. 8 presented an impact on Q_{Mg} , increasing the charge associated with Mg oxidation for the AZ31 Mg alloy significantly with respect to the AZ61 and, particularly, the AZ91 Mg alloy.

3.3. Validation of the kinetic model to explain anomalous HE

The fact that the anomalous HE current densities for the Mg alloys used in this study (see Fig. 6) showed a direct correlation with the amount of charge associated with the Mg oxidation reaction in the same materials is consistent with the model proposed by Fajardo and Frankel [24]. This model assumes that the anomalous HE originates exclusively at the anodic regions, and that higher Mg oxidation current density leads to higher surface fraction of regions undergoing active dissolution (see Eq. (1)). Therefore, greater anodic polarization leads to a larger number of active Mg sites available for oxidation and the concomitant anomalous HE.

The kinetic model proposed by Fajardo and Frankel [24] indicates that, for the anomalous HE to occur, the charge transfer coefficient associated with the Mg alloy oxidation reaction (α_{Mg}) needs to be greater than the charge transfer coefficient for the HER (α_{HER}). Consequently, to determine α_{Mg} and α_{HER} , the Tafel slopes associated with the Mg oxidation reaction (b_{Mg}) and the HER (b_{HER}), respectively, need to be calculated. Fig. 11 shows the galvanodynamic polarization signal associated with the oxidation reaction and the HER on the AZ31 Mg alloy in 0.1 M NaCl solution plotted as a function of the measured potential. Note that the kinetics of the anodic reaction are the real Mg alloy oxidation current density values, determined by the addition of the applied anodic and the HE current densities measured using the gravimetric method (Fig. 6). In Fig. 11 only typical data for the AZ31 Mg alloy are shown as an example of the analysis that was carried out to determine b_{Mg} and b_{HER} for all the Mg alloys used in this study.

One of the main limitations in the determination of the Tafel slopes of Mg and its alloys is that HE occurs both under anodic and cathodic polarization. This evolution of H_2 increases as the applied current density increases, creating large ohmic potential drops that distort the shape of the polarization response. It is very difficult to compensate for the ohmic

drop by the current interrupt method because of the excessive HE. For this reason, the measured potential values plotted in Fig. 11 are not corrected for ohmic potential drop. However, to minimize the effects of ohmic drops and with the aim of determining the Tafel slopes consistently between all different measurements, the Tafel regions were systematically determined before the bending of the curve, within the range of 50 mV to 250 mV from the E_{corr} for both the anodic and cathodic curves. It is observed in Fig. 11 that the calculated b_{Mg} and b_{HER} for the AZ31 Mg alloy were $+0.149 \pm 0.007$ and -0.152 ± 0.007 V/decade, respectively. Table 2 shows the Tafel slopes determined using the analysis in Fig. 11 for the AZ31, AZ61 and AZ91 Mg alloys in 0.1 M NaCl solution. It should be mentioned that the Tafel slopes associated with the HER calculated in this analysis were lower than reported in a previous paper for HP Mg [24]. However, they are in good agreement with those reported by other authors for different AZ Mg alloys (i.e. AZ31 and AZ91) [33].

Interestingly, the Tafel slopes associated with the Mg alloy oxidation reaction decreased with increasing the concentration of Al, suggesting that the anodic kinetics were higher for the AZ91 than for the AZ31 Mg alloy, which contradicts the results in Fig. 6. However, this is probably due to the following reasons: a) polarization measurements were performed under current control, which did not allow for the passivating effect of Al to manifest; b) the lower rates of anomalous HE measured on the AZ91 Mg alloy likely caused smaller ohmic potential drops than in the case of the AZ61 and the AZ31 Mg alloy.

From b_{Mg} and b_{HER} and assuming activation controlled kinetics, it is possible to determine α_{Mg} and α_{HER} using the following relation [34]:

$$b_{\text{Mg}} = 2.3 \frac{RT}{\alpha_{\text{Mg}} zF} \quad (5)$$

$$|b_{\text{HER}}| = 2.3 \frac{RT}{\alpha_{\text{HER}} z F} \quad (6)$$

where b_{HER} is expressed as absolute value and the rest of the terms have been described previously or have their usual meaning. Using the calculated Tafel slopes and assuming 25° C, $\alpha_{\text{Mg}} = 0.21 \pm 0.01$ and $\alpha_{\text{HER}} = 0.18 \pm 0.01$ for the AZ31 Mg alloy. Table 2 also shows the charge transfer coefficients determined from the Tafel slopes calculated using the analysis in Fig. 11 for the AZ61 and AZ91 Mg alloys in 0.1 M NaCl solution. In summary, the reproducible experimental data on the AZ31, AZ61 and AZ91 Mg alloys anodically polarized in 0.1 M NaCl used in this study, satisfy the condition that $\alpha_{\text{Mg}} > \alpha_{\text{HER}}$, which validates the model proposed by Fajardo and Frankel [24], further confirming that the anomalous HE exhibited by Mg and its alloys is primarily associated with the regions of active dissolution.

4. Conclusions

The anomalous HE on AZ31, AZ61 and AZ91 Mg alloys was investigated using galvanodynamic polarization, gravimetric H₂ collection and potentiodynamic polarization measurements in unbuffered 0.1 M NaCl solution. The following can be concluded:

- Strong anomalous HE was observed on the AZ31, AZ61 and AZ91 Mg alloys, exhibiting a linear dependence of the HE current density on the applied anodic current density.
- The rate of anomalous HE measured under anodic polarization showed a clear dependence on the concentration of Al in the Mg alloy. The amount of charge associated with the anomalous HE was inversely proportional to the amount of Al in the alloy.
- Greater concentrations of Al in the Mg alloys lead to a higher surface fraction of β -phase in the alloys, reducing the number of available sites for Mg oxidation and concomitant anomalous HE.

- Dissolution of the β -phase during galvanodynamic anodic polarization of the AZ Mg alloys reduced the charge associated with Mg oxidation, which may be associated with reduced rates of anomalous HE.
- Surface appearance of previously polarized surfaces showed that corrosion product coverage depended on the concentration of Al in the alloy. The amount of corrosion products was the greatest on the AZ31 surface and decreased significantly with increasing Al content. However, no significant differences were observed in the cathodic potentiodynamic response between the 3 alloys that had been previously subjected to anodic polarization. This is not consistent with the notion that the corrosion products are responsible for the anomalous HE.
- The charge transfer coefficient for the magnesium dissolution reaction was greater than that for the HE reaction for all three alloys. This supports the prediction of the kinetic model proposed previously based on the notion that the anomalous HE exhibited on anodically polarized Mg originates at the actively dissolving Mg regions.

Acknowledgements

S. Fajardo expresses his gratitude to the State Research Agency (Ministry of Science, Technology and Universities of Spain), the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) and the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) for the financial support under the Project MAT2015-74420-JIN (AEI/FEDER/UE). The authors thank J.C. Galván for supplying the AZ91 Mg alloy.

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Table 1. Chemical composition (wt. %) of the Mg alloys used. The balance was Mg.

Material	Al	Zn	Mn	Si	Cu	Fe	Ni	Ca	Zr	Others
AZ31	3.1	0.73	0.25	0.02	<0.001	0.005	<0.001	0.0014	<0.001	<0.30
AZ61	6.2	0.74	0.23	0.04	<0.001	0.004	<0.001	0.0013	<0.001	<0.30
AZ91	9.4	0.82	0.20	<0.05	<0.025	<0.004	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.30

Table 2. Tafel slopes and charge transfer coefficients associated with the Mg oxidation reaction (b_{Mg} , α_{Mg}) and the HER ($|b_{\text{HER}}|$, α_{HER}) for the AZ31, AZ61 and AZ91 Mg alloys during galvanodynamic anodic and cathodic polarization, respectively, in 0.1 M NaCl solution. Calculations were carried out according to the analysis in Fig. 11.

Material	b_{Mg} (V/dec)	$ b_{\text{HER}} $ (V/dec)	α_{Mg}	α_{HER}
AZ31	0.144 ± 0.005	-0.165 ± 0.009	0.21 ± 0.01	0.18 ± 0.01
AZ61	0.075 ± 0.005	-0.158 ± 0.004	0.39 ± 0.03	0.187 ± 0.004
AZ91	0.049 ± 0.003	-0.167 ± 0.004	0.60 ± 0.04	0.176 ± 0.004

Fig. 1. Hydrogen evolution current density for the AZ31 Mg alloy in 0.1 M NaCl solution during (a) anodic galvanodynamic polarization, and (b) cathodic galvanodynamic polarization, as a function of the applied current density. HE current densities were calculated from gravimetric measurements during galvanodynamic polarization. The scan rate was 0.1 mA/cm² s. Data from triplicate experiments are presented. Current density is presented as absolute value.

Fig. 2. Hydrogen evolution current density for the AZ61 Mg alloy in 0.1 M NaCl solution during (a) anodic galvanodynamic polarization, and (b) cathodic galvanodynamic polarization, as a function of the applied current density. HE current densities were calculated from gravimetric measurements during galvanodynamic polarization. The scan rate was 0.1 mA/cm² s. Data from triplicate experiments are presented. Current density is presented as absolute value.

Fig. 3. Hydrogen evolution current density for the AZ91 Mg alloy in 0.1 M NaCl solution during (a) anodic galvanodynamic polarization, and (b) cathodic galvanodynamic polarization, as a function of the applied current density. HE current densities were calculated from gravimetric measurements during galvanodynamic polarization. The scan rate was 0.1 mA/cm² s. Data from triplicate experiments are presented. Current density is presented as absolute value.

Fig. 4. Hydrogen evolution current density for the AZ31 Mg alloy in 0.1 M NaCl solution during anodic galvanodynamic polarization as a function of the applied current density: (a) typical curve from the reproducible raw data in Fig. 1(a); and (b) second-order smoothed curve. Black dashed lines are the linear fit of each curve. Current density is presented as absolute value.

Fig. 5. Hydrogen evolution current density for the AZ31 Mg alloy in 0.1 M NaCl solution during cathodic galvanodynamic polarization as a function of the applied current density: (a) typical curve from the reproducible raw data in Fig. 1(b); and (b) second-order smoothed curve. Black dashed lines are the linear fit of each curve. Current density is presented as absolute value.

Fig. 6. Hydrogen evolution current density for the AZ31, AZ61 and AZ91 Mg alloys in 0.1 M NaCl solution during anodic galvanodynamic polarization as a function of the applied current density. HE current densities were calculated from the second-order smoothed curves in Figs. 1(a), 2(a) and 3(a). Mean values from triplicate experiments for each material are presented. Error bars are standard deviation. Current density is presented as absolute value.

Fig. 7. Charge density associated with anomalous HE normalized to the net charge density for the AZ31, AZ61 and AZ91 Mg alloys electrodes in 0.1 M NaCl solution. The net charge density passed was 12.5 C/cm² in all cases. Mean values from replicated experiments are presented. The error bars are standard deviation.

Fig. 8. Surface appearance of the AZ31, AZ61 and AZ91 Mg alloys after galvanodynamic anodic polarization up to 50 mA/cm^2 in 0.1 M NaCl solution.

Fig. 9. Potential measured during galvanodynamic anodic polarization of the AZ31, AZ61 and AZ91 Mg alloys electrodes in 0.1 M NaCl solution as a function of the polarization time. Dashed line represents the E_{corr} for the $Mg_{17}Al_{12}$ second phase (β -phase) in 0.1 M NaCl solution ($-1.311 V_{SSC}$) [30]. Mean values from replicated experiments are presented. The error bars are standard deviation.

Fig. 10. Cathodic potentiodynamic polarization curves for the AZ31, AZ61 and AZ91 Mg alloys in 0.1 M NaCl solution after galvanodynamic anodic polarization up to 50 mA/cm². Cathodic potentiodynamic polarization measurements were carried out immediately after prior anodic polarization was finished. Cathodic potentiodynamic polarization curves for the AZ31, AZ61 and AZ91 Mg alloys in 0.1 M NaCl solution without prior anodic polarization are also presented for comparative purposes. Experiments were performed starting from the OCP at a potential scan rate of 1 mV/s. Typical data from replicated experiments are presented. Current density is presented as absolute value.

Fig. 11. Galvanodynamic polarization curves of AZ31 Mg alloy in 0.1 M NaCl solution. The anodic polarization curve (a) represents the real Mg oxidation current density determined by the addition of the applied anodic and the HE current densities measured using the gravimetric method (Fig. 6). The cathodic polarization curve (b) is the current density obtained by the potentiostat during cathodic galvanodynamic polarization. Typical data from replicated experiments are presented. Potential values are not corrected for ohmic potential drop. Current density is presented as absolute value.